

Community Recommendation for a Persistent Identifier (PID) Policy for the European Open Science Cloud

Version 2.0

Editors

Tibor Kálmán¹ (GWDG), Marek Cebecauer² (Heyrovsky Institute), Natascha van Lieshout³ (SURF), Josefine Nordling⁴ (CSC), Ulriika Vihervalli⁵ (CSC), Themis Zamani⁶ (GRNET).

Members of the EOSC Opportunity Area 1 Expert Group: Persistent Identifiers

Raed Al Zoubi (ASREN), Mike Bennett (DataCite), Sharon Bolton (University of Essex), Marek Cebecauer (Heyrovsky Institute), Ellie DeSota (DeSci Labs), Gorka Epelde (Biogipuzkoa), Beate Guba (TU Wien), Margareta Hellström (Lund University), Wim Hugo (DANS), Nick Juty (University of Manchester), Tibor Kálmán (GWDG), Evdokimos Konstantinidis (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki), Paolo Lai (CNRS Inist), Natascha van Lieshout (SURF), Gabriela Mejias (DataCite), Paul Millar (DESY), Adam Vials Moore (Jisc), Josefine Nordling (CSC), Michal Růžička (Masaryk University), Tommi Suominen (CSC), Daniel Turner (DCC), Ulriika Vihervalli (CSC), Themis Zamani (GRNET)

¹ ORCID: [0000-0001-5194-5053](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5194-5053)

² ORCID: [0000-0002-4606-1218](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4606-1218)

³ ORCID: [0000-0001-8025-8412](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8025-8412)

⁴ ORCID: [0000-0002-6974-2825](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6974-2825)

⁵ ORCID: [0000-0003-3584-357X](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3584-357X)

⁶ ORCID: [0000-0003-1148-1738](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1148-1738)

Coordinator

Tibor Kálmán (GWDG)

Task Force Support Officer

Brina Klemenčič (EOSC-A)

Reviewers

Ignacio Blanquer (EOSC-A Director), Jessica Parland-von Essen (CSC), Miguel Rey Mazón (TU Graz)

Document background

This document is an output of the EOSC Opportunity Area 1 Expert Group (OAEG1): Persistent Identifiers. The EOSC OAEG1 Persistent Identifiers is one of the seven Expert Groups under the EOSC Association⁷. A key objective of OAEG1 is to update the EOSC PID policy to outline requirements for new projects, foster community consensus on PID standardisation, and advance the adoption of persistent identifiers within the EOSC.

The expert group brings together over 20 experts on persistent identifiers from 20 organisations across 12 countries. These experts represent national, regional, European, and international initiatives, as well as the former members of the EOSC-A PID Policy and Implementation Task Force. Further information regarding OAEG1's objectives, activities, and the Expert Group's membership can be found on the EOSC Opportunity Area 1 Expert Group: Persistent Identifiers web page⁸.

⁷ <https://eosc.eu/>

⁸ <https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa1-persistent-identifiers/>

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Executive summary

This Persistent Identifier (PID) policy is written for senior decision makers within existing and potential EOSC service and infrastructure providers and supports all EOSC stakeholders. It defines a set of expectations about what persistent identifiers are, and how they will be used to support a well-functioning FAIR⁹-compliant research environment. Requirements for providers and the basic services they offer are also outlined. This PID policy also serves as a guideline to align different PID implementations enabling an interoperable identification of resources for FAIR research.

The first version of the PID Policy¹⁰ (version 1.0) was developed by representatives of the EOSC FAIR Working Group and the EOSC Architecture Working Group. The EOSC Executive Board approved this version in 2020. The PID Policy was then continuously further developed (version 1.1 and 1.2) by the PID Policy and Implementation Task Force of the EOSC Association (EOSC-A PID TF¹¹) during its mandate between 2021–2023. Various projects were consulted (FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT, RAISE), and feedback from the events EOSC Symposium 2023, International Data Week 2023, and EOSC Winter School 2024 was collected and incorporated. This current version (version 2.0) is a revision continued from EOSC-A PID TF efforts, and authored by the EOSC Opportunity Area 1 Expert Group: Persistent Identifiers (OAEG1 PID¹²). It incorporates valuable feedback from the EOSC Symposium 2024 and EOSC Winter School 2025, but does not yet reflect the current discussions of the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation.

This document sets out to inform the use of PIDs in the EOSC ecosystem, providing an overview of PID terminology, structures, types and governance. EOSC-affiliated organisations should use this document to inform their own PID policies. The current version (v2.0) of the PID Policy is not yet approved by the EOSC Association or the relevant EOSC governing body; and as such, it is not an official EOSC policy document, but a community recommendation.

⁹ Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

¹⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, & EOSC Executive Board. (2020). *A Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037>

¹¹ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/pid-policy-implementation/>

¹² <https://eosc.eu/opportunity-area-exp/oa1-persistent-identifiers>

1 Context

1.1 This Persistent Identifier (PID) policy is written for senior decision makers within potential EOSC service and infrastructure providers, and will be of interest to all EOSC stakeholders. It defines a set of expectations about what persistent identifiers are and how they will be used to support a functioning environment of FAIR research. The requirements of providers and the basic services they offer are also outlined.

1.2 Many types of Persistent Identifiers are already in active use for a range of applications. In addition, numerous technologies, databases and cloud systems use local identifiers. This PID policy does not make detailed statements about existing systems, but offers definitions, guidelines, and usage requirements.

1.3 The GDPR regulations shape the use of PIDs that store and provide personal data. PID Service Providers should be GDPR compliant. The GDPR grants data subjects certain rights, including the right to ask organisations to delete their personal data (right to erasure). Since PIDs are exchanged and used by different entities (repositories, research-performing organisations, research infrastructures, EOSC, etc.), data subjects will have to exercise their rights under the GDPR (such as the right to erasure) on a case-by-case basis. In practice, it is likely to be difficult for data subjects to track where their personal data is processed.

2 Principles

2.1 The PID Policy concentrates on principles, desired results and governance which are designed to establish a viable, trusted PID infrastructure suitable for the long-term sustainability of the EOSC.

2.2 This PID Policy accommodates a wide range of use cases, both for human use and machine-actionability, and does not put in place barriers to the effective use of PIDs as needed by the research community.

2.3 This PID Policy promotes the use of PIDs as the preferred means of referencing entities, complemented where appropriate by human-readable names, supporting human-readable names (e.g. common names). Multiple PIDs may exist for a single entity, and users may use the identifier most suitable for their context (see [Section 3.6](#) for handling overlaps). While embedding semantics in PID strings is not encouraged, it may be acceptable where justified. However, the long-term implications of using human-readable elements should be carefully considered).

2.4 The PID Policy aims to enable a research environment that aligns with the FAIR principles tailored to the specific needs of different domains. Central to the realisation of these principles are FAIR Digital Objects, and PIDs are core to the idea of FAIR Digital Objects as highlighted in the Turning FAIR Into Reality report¹³, as well as in the EOSC Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR) 2025 and 2026–2027.

2.5 To create a well-functioning PID ecosystem and realise the FAIR Principles, the PID Policy maximises the interoperability between PID Services, PID Service Providers, as well as across research infrastructures.

2.6 Technology independence of PIDs is necessary to allow for future developments and technological change. PID services will vary in maturity over time, and the PID policy should identify the level of service maturity suitable for EOSC adoption.

2.7 The policy seeks to accommodate mature and established PID practices, schemes, technologies and providers which have a global presence. The policy also needs to be balanced and not prefer one approach or technology over another.

2.8 By adhering to the policy, PID Providers and users commit to sustaining PID infrastructures and Digital Objects, which are digital representations of physical or abstract entities, in the long term. They also commit to engaging in risk and lifecycle management.

2.9 The Policy aims to encourage new and innovative services and tools which use and build on the PID Infrastructure.

2.10 The policy is maintained by the EOSC governance that governs the endorsed policies of EOSC, and it is reviewed by a dedicated group of appropriate experts and stakeholders on a regular basis (e.g. OAEG1 of EOSC-A).

3 Generic PID definitions

This section defines the core characteristics of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) that support FAIR research within the EOSC ecosystem. A PID must be globally unique, persistent, and resolvable; ensuring that identified entities can be reliably referenced and accessed over time. Global uniqueness

¹³ European Commission Expert Group on FAIR Data (2018)

is achieved through controlled syntax and namespace governance, while persistence requires stable management, governance, and long-term trust in the identifier and its underlying schema. Persistence also applies to the relationship between the PID and the entity it identifies, including appropriate handling of versioning and changes to the referent. Resolvable PIDs must enable access to information in the PID record for both human and machine users, even if the original entity is no longer available. In such cases, tombstone information should be provided to maintain reference integrity. Together, these principles ensure that PID systems support reliable identification, interoperability, and the broader goal of enabling FAIR research practices.

3.1 For the purposes of this Policy, a Persistent Identifier that supports and enables FAIR research is one that is globally unique, persistent, and resolvable. Each of these three features may be delivered through various means and technologies, but some basic principles apply.

3.2 Globally Unique

3.2.1 To enable global uniqueness, a PID should comply with a controlled syntax to avoid clashes. For instance, by having namespaces that are governed by clearly defined PID Authorities (see [Section 4.4](#)).

3.3 Persistent

3.3.1 Persistence relates to three aspects. The first two relate directly to the PID itself, and the last to the entity or representation to which it refers.

3.3.1.1 The PID should be managed and governed in such a way that the community can trust it to remain unique and resolvable in the long-term. This may be beyond the lifetime of the entity it identifies, the creators of that entity, or even the PID service provider itself. The latter point is dependent on fulfilling [8.4](#).

3.3.1.2 The controlled syntax schema should be stable and maintained. Backwards compatibility should be supported when possible. To enable this, versions of the controlled syntax schema (which are themselves digital objects) must have associated PIDs. When applicable, Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) of PID Services should also follow these prescriptions.

3.3.1.3 Persistence also relates to the entity or representation to which the PID resolves (i.e. the “referent”). The referent should also be stable (see exceptions in the next subsection), whether it is a digital object or a digital representation of a physical or abstract entity. In

some cases, immutability of the referent is required, e.g. for a dataset in support of research that should not change to ensure reproducibility; and in other cases, the entity as it is currently understood is maintained, for example, an institution that has changed over time. This meaning of persistence should also be considered in conjunction with versioning (see [Section 5.5](#) and [Section 5.6](#)).

3.4 Resolvable

3.4.1 A PID is resolvable when it allows both human and machine users to access:

3.4.1.1 A digital object, a digital representation of an entity, or information on how the entity can be accessed.

3.4.1.2 Kernel Information: A global resolution system should support access to Kernel Information from its PID. In general, the Kernel Information should at least contain attributes that point to where the bit sequence of the referent can be found, and a pointer to a type definition. Optionally, it may contain pointers to further contextual entities, including metadata. Type definitions, PID Kernel Information Profiles should be registered in open registries.

3.4.1.3 When an entity or its representation is no longer available, resolution to Kernel Information must still be possible. Kernel Information (see [Section 5.6](#)) should thus include tombstone information in such cases.

3.4.1.4 There will be instances where, for legal reasons, sensitive information about the referent must be deleted. For example, following a right-to-erasure request by a data subject under GDPR. In such cases, resolvability should still be maintained to tombstone information that provides as much Kernel Information as possible, while remaining compliant with applicable legal requirements.

3.4.2 EOSC should only accept PIDs that can be resolved globally. To make PIDs globally resolvable, the PID needs to be part of a namespace defined by a syntax that is controlled by a PID Authority (see [Section 4.4](#)).

3.5 The use (or application) and management of the PID, and its related services and governance, should endeavour to follow the FAIR principles.

3.6 This policy is purposefully neutral on the practice of more than one PID referring to the same entity (but see also [Section 2.3](#)). Kernel Information should support understanding of known overlaps through the use of optional SameAs, AlsoKnownAs or KnownAs attributes.

4 Roles and responsibilities

The roles and responsibilities defined in this section ensure a robust and consistent framework for the use, management, and governance of PIDs within the EOSC Federation. These roles clarify who is responsible for assigning, maintaining, resolving, and governing PIDs. The ecosystem can be visualised as a network of nodes (entities – roles) and edges (relations - labelled with their respective roles), showing how components in the PID stack interact to support persistent access, interoperability, and discoverability of resources. Figure 1 illustrates this network. In the following, we describe these entities and the relations briefly.

Figure 1. PID Ecosystem entities and relations between them¹⁴

¹⁴ Source: Hugo et al. (2023).

4.1 A PID Infrastructure within the EOSC ecosystem should define several roles which actors can undertake. Each role is responsible for a particular component within the PID Infrastructure, with particular commitments to maintaining the integrity of that PID Infrastructure. Actors can play more than one role, or undertake actions associated with multiple roles, under particular circumstances, but for the sake of clarity, it is useful to describe the main characteristics of all roles separately.

4.2 A PID Infrastructure is formed by several components, including services, rules or standards, that enable the Infrastructure to operate according to the policies and expectations of its target communities.

4.3 PID Schema (Component). A set of rules and standards defining the nature of a PID, including a set of lexical formatting rules for PIDs within a namespace. A Schema may define the types of PIDs associated with it, define associated metadata, quality assurance conditions, usage rights, terms and conditions, and algorithmic methods for generating PID names and enforcing PID properties. The PID metadata schema should be machine-actionable.

4.4 PID Authority (Role). An organisation (e.g. DOI.org) or decentralised community mechanism (for example, SWHIDs – Software Hash Identifiers (SWHIDs)¹⁵ – and W3C’s Decentralised Identifiers) responsible for maintaining the rules for defining the integrity of PIDs within a PID Schema. The rules may include setting standards for lexical formats, algorithms and protocols to ensure global uniqueness, together with setting quality of service conditions to enforce compliance with the rules. PID Authorities led by organisations typically enforce control over a PID infrastructure, while decentralised solutions provide community standardisation mechanisms that specify how PIDs conform to a PID Schema.

4.5 PID Service Provider (Role). An organisation which provides PID Services in conformance to a PID Schema, subject to the corresponding PID Authority. PID Service Providers are responsible for the provision, integrity, reliability and scalability of PID Services, in particular the issuing and resolution of PIDs, but also lookup and search services, and interoperability with generic resolution systems, e.g. the PID MetaResolver.

4.6 PID Service (Component). Basic services are those that create, manage and resolve PIDs and their associated Kernel Information, which conforms to a PID Schema. Advanced, value-added services may also be provided, for example, attribute search or metrics.

¹⁵ Software Hash Identifiers are intrinsic identifiers which enable decentralised operations and independent integrity verification. The SWHID Project entails the development and maintenance of the SWHID specification, software and other related content.

4.7 PID Manager (Role). PID Managers are responsible for maintaining the integrity of the relationship between an entity and the PID(s) that refer to it, according to a PID Schema defined by a PID Authority. A PID Manager will typically subscribe to PID Services to offer functionality to PID Owners within the PID Manager’s services. PID Managers encompass data repository, data catalogue, or research workflow system providers.

4.8 PID Owner (Role). An actor (an organisation or individual) who has the control to create a PID, assign a PID to an entity, and provide and maintain accurate Kernel Information or Custom Metadata for the PID. PID Owners SHOULD comply with the policies and contractual arrangements for transfer of ownership set by the PID manager. If the current PID Owner is no longer able to carry out its responsibilities, then a new PID Owner must be identified.

4.9 End User (Role). The end user is an actor, for example, a researcher, software or service that creates, resolves and uses the information contained in PIDs either directly or indirectly.

5 PID applications

This section outlines the functional expectations for PID applications and services within the EOSC ecosystem. The PID infrastructure should support a diverse range of applications through interoperable services, including standard APIs that enable core operations such as creating, resolving, and modifying PIDs and their Kernel Information. PID Services must also accommodate varying community needs, including secure handling of sensitive metadata, different levels of entity granularity, and evolving use cases. Clear roles and responsibilities are defined for PID owners, managers, and service providers to ensure the integrity, visibility, and proper maintenance of PID records. Providers should support community feedback mechanisms, implement versioning practices, and publish guidance on appropriate use cases. Finally, PIDs must remain persistent and cannot be deleted or reassigned, with mechanisms such as tombstone records ensuring continued access to Kernel Information even when the identified entity no longer exists.

5.1 An ecosystem of PID Infrastructures is needed to support a wide variety of applications and offer sufficient flexibility (service providers, schema, attribute sets) and capacity for emergent needs).

Service providers SHOULD provide a common Application Programming Interface (API)¹⁶ to interact with PIDs, supporting a minimum set of operations (create, resolve and modify PID record). The requirements that need to be met by APIs SHOULD be defined by the governing bodies of the EOSC Federation, based on the input of appropriate experts (e.g. OAEG1 of EOSC-A).

5.2 PID Service Providers for EOSC need to address a wide variety of applications, including those that require secure mechanisms built into the PID Infrastructure.

PID Service Providers SHOULD provide support for access control and/or encryption of the Kernel Information for sensitive metadata

5.3 PID ownership MUST be visible to other actors in the ecosystem.

PID Owners SHOULD maintain PID attributes.

PID Managers MUST provide the functionality required to maintain PID attributes.

PID Managers SHOULD provide policies and contractual arrangements for the transfer of ownership should the owner no longer be able to assume responsibilities in compliance with the policy.

PID Managers MUST maintain the integrity of the relationship between entities and their PIDs, in conformance to a PID Schema defined by a PID Authority.

5.4 The PID ecosystem will need to contend with the different and evolving requirements of communities with respect to the granularity of identified entities. As this ecosystem evolves, thought must be given to the increasing costs and efforts, related to the increase in the volume and complexity of PIDs.

The PID Service Providers SHOULD publish guidance on which use cases, levels of granularity, and community best practices are satisfied by the PID Services they provide.

5.5 PID Service Providers SHOULD put feedback mechanisms in place to enable End Users propose changes to the Services they provide, and adjust their services and guidance accordingly.

5.6 PID Services SHOULD support versioning for both Kernel Metadata and for the entity or concept being referenced by the PID.

¹⁶ The RDA Working Groups on PID Information Types and PID Kernel Information have produced preliminary recommendations and prototypes for such an interface and principles for Kernel Information that can form the basis for further work.

PID Service Providers and PID Managers SHOULD have clear versioning policies.

5.7 PID Authority MUST ensure that the PID cannot be deleted, and that PIDs are not repurposed. PID Service Providers MUST therefore ensure in their implementations that the PID issued by the PID Authority cannot be deleted from its records. PID Managers MUST ensure that the entity remains linked to the PID. In case the entity being identified is deleted or ceases to exist, PID Managers MUST provide tombstone information in the PID attribute set.

5.8 PID Authorities SHOULD provide information on the referenced entity's fundamental type and management policy in a machine-actionable way.

6 PID entity types

This section describes the different types of entities that Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) can represent within the EOSC ecosystem. PIDs may be assigned to digital, physical, or conceptual entities, provided that physical and conceptual entities are represented through a digital form such as metadata records or landing pages. These digital representations should follow the principles of FAIR Digital Objects to ensure they remain findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. PID Services are expected to work with their communities to define appropriate Kernel Information Profiles that support specific use cases. In addition, PID Service Providers must ensure that entity metadata is maintained as accurately as possible in collaboration with PID owners and managers, with clearly defined authoritative sources for both custom metadata and kernel information.

6.1 PIDs MAY identify many different entities. These can be tied to: (1) digital entities and collections made of them (e.g. documents, data, software, services - otherwise known as digital objects); (2) physical entities (e.g. people, instruments, artefacts, samples), or (3) conceptual entities (e.g. organisations, projects, semantic artefacts, vocabularies).

6.2 Physical and conceptual entities MUST be represented with a digital representation (e.g. landing page, metadata, attribute set, database index) to have a presence in the digital landscape. All digital representations should be FAIR Digital Objects.

6.3 PID Services MUST engage the relevant stakeholder communities to develop one or more Kernel Information Profiles appropriate to the use cases addressed by their services.

6.4 The PID Service MUST maintain entity metadata as accurately as possible in collaboration with the PID Owner. The metadata maintained by the PID Owner, with assistance from the PID Manager, is authoritative. If only Kernel Metadata exists, that is the authoritative source. The maintenance of PID Kernel Information is related to versioning. More information on versioning can be found in [Section 5.6](#).

7 PID services and PID service providers

This section outlines expectations for PID Services and PID Service Providers operating in the EOSC ecosystem. PID Services should be broadly accessible to the research community, interoperable with research infrastructures, and provide core functions such as PID registration and resolution free of charge. Providers must ensure that their services are technically mature, reliable, and highly available, while maintaining clear operational documentation and management processes for PID records and metadata. They are also expected to ensure the long-term sustainability of PID management, including continuity of PID resolution through succession planning. In addition, PID Service Providers must participate in regular compliance assessments with EOSC policies and enable interoperability with emerging global PID resolution systems by supporting metadata exchange and integration mechanisms.

7.1 PID Services MUST be able to interoperate seamlessly with European Research Infrastructures, but not at the exclusion of the broader research community.

PID Services SHOULD be accessible to all researchers in the EU. Some functionalities may be adapted to region- or country-specific conditions.

The basic services of PID registration and resolution SHALL have no cost to end users.

7.2 As with other EOSC core services, the basic functionalities (registration, resolution) of a PID Service infrastructure MUST be at a minimum TRL of 8.¹⁷

However, added-value PID Services (e.g., metadata catalogues, knowledge graph extensions, etc.) MAY be offered at technology readiness levels lower than 8.

7.3 Basic functionalities of PID Services MUST meet 999 (99.9% or “24/7”) availability and uptime.¹⁸

PID Service Providers SHOULD provide publicly accessible documentation of their maintenance activities and availability provisions. PID Service Providers SHOULD keep a log of events, including the

¹⁷ <https://enspire.science/trl-scale-horizon-europe-erc-explained/>

¹⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/High_availability

history of edits to the PID record metadata (where applicable). PID Service Providers SHOULD agree with PID Managers on the responsibilities for Kernel Information maintenance, preferably via contracts.

7.4 PID Authorities and PID Service Providers MUST agree to be assessed with a mutually agreed frequency in respect of policy compliance. The assessments should cover both the resolvability of PIDs to information from PID Service Providers and their management processes for the maintenance of PIDs (for example, by applying the Compliance Assessment Toolkit, CAT).¹⁹

7.5 Generic global PID resolution systems, able to work across all PID systems and service providers, are being developed. To enable such metaresolvers, PID Service Providers MUST ensure their systems are able to exchange relevant metadata (through APIs) with global resolution services.²⁰

8 Governance and sustainability

This section outlines the governance and sustainability expectations for PID Services operating within the EOSC ecosystem. PID governance structures must include representation from the European research community and ensure that services operate in accordance with the EOSC PID Policy, support global interoperability, and align with the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure (POSI). PID Services should be offered at transparent and justifiable costs to PID owners and managers, while avoiding disproportionate pricing differences between EOSC and non-EOSC users. Service providers must also maintain clear sustainability strategies and publicly verifiable exit plans to ensure the long-term continuity and resolvability of PIDs. In addition, EOSC should foster the development and adoption of new PID Services and tools, supporting the continued growth and resilience of the PID ecosystem.

8.1 PID governance structures MUST include representatives of the European research community. The activities SHOULD also be aligned and coordinated at a global level.

8.2 PID Services SHOULD be available at justifiable cost to PID Owners and PID Managers within EOSC. This SHOULD NOT result in significantly higher costs for usage outside EOSC.

¹⁹ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/compliance-assessment-toolkit-cat>

²⁰ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/eosc-core-components/eosc-pid-meta-resolver-pidmr>

8.3 The governance structures of PID Service Providers MUST ensure their PID Services and Systems adhere to the EOSC PID Policy, enable global interoperability, and that they are compatible with the Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure. A coordination mechanism for EOSC PID Service Providers SHOULD be established²¹.

8.4 PID Service Providers MUST have a public and independently verifiable exit plan and sustainability strategy that assures the continuity of the resolution of PIDs registered with their service. This plan will allow other providers to replicate the PIDs and services if the original provider ceases to operate.

8.5 The EOSC SHOULD encourage the development and adoption of new PID Services and tools. This can be measured indirectly through indicators such as the number and growth of PID Services available.

²¹ Mejjas, G., Cousijn, H., Marjamaa-Mankinen, L., Nordling, J., van Lieshout, N., & Gonzalez-Beltran, A. (2023). *M3.2 - Proposal for an EOSC PID Service providers coordination mechanism*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8405818>

Appendix 1: List of sources consulted

This is a list of existing publications, policies, recommendations and other texts consulted in the authoring of this policy statement.

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Appendix 2: Glossary

These terms are provided to aid understanding of the policy, and are in addition to definitions of roles and responsibilities defined in [Section 4](#). All terms need to be seen in relation to PIDs.

Attribute	A value that describes a feature of an entity or its representation, as part of PID Kernel Information or other metadata.
Digital Entity	A Digital Entity denotes any sort of bit sequence that is stored or transmitted without being registered to enable sharing.
Digital Object	A Digital Object has a bit sequence that can be stored in multiple repositories and is associated with a Persistent Identifier (PID) and metadata.
European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)	An integrated infrastructure and “system of systems” approach to create a “Web of FAIR Data and Services”. The development of EOSC is a large and ongoing multi-stakeholder initiative.
FAIR Digital Object	FAIR Digital Objects (FDO) bind all critical information about an entity in one place and create a new kind of actionable, meaningful and technology-independent entity that pervades every aspect of life today: A technical essence of a “thing” in cyberspace.
FAIR Principles	FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. It refers to the FAIR Data Principles developed by the FORCE 11 community, which recommend that data should be shared according to these four concepts.
GDPR	The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is a European Union law that provides a uniform framework for protecting personal data.

Granularity	The varying levels of hierarchy or constituent parts that may form data or other research outputs. For example, the differing levels of granularity of a research publication, going from a whole Journal issue, to its constituent articles, to the article's constituent sections or figures, the levels in a complex scientific collection or the level of detail in a large scientific database.
Kernel Information	A structured record consisting of well-defined attributes to allow machine actions. PIDs resolve to these structured records.
Landing Page	A human-readable page, displayed in a browser, that provides human users with information on how to access and/or interpret the digital object or its representation that is identified by a PID.
Machine Actionable	Machine Actionable means that a formal statement is syntactically and semantically specified, enabling computing systems to carry out automatic processing.
Metadata	With metadata in the context of this PID policy, we mean all kinds of assertions about properties of the bit sequence of a digital object, such as descriptive, deep scientific, contextual, provenance, access permissions, transactions, etc. This kind of metadata is not stored in the PID record as Kernel attributes; however, the PID record in general should point to the metadata.
Multi-Primary Administrator (MPA)	Each credentialed MPA operates its own GHR Services in accordance with the DONA Foundation Policies & Procedures for the GHR, and coordinates its GHR Services with other MPAs and DONA in the distributed operation of the GHR on a multi-primary basis (applies only to DOI and Handle).
Namespace	A namespace ensures that all identifiers within a given level have unique names, allowing them to be easily identified.

Persistent Identifier (PID)	A persistent, unique and globally resolvable identifier that is based on an openly specified PID Schema.
PID Ecosystem	The set of PID Components and Services that may be federated or interoperable to support EOSC and research that is FAIR in an effective and sustainable way.
PID Kernel Information Profile	The PID Kernel Information Profile describes the set of Kernel attributes that are being selected by a repository to describe the DO. The profile is dependent on the type of entity and the needs of the community. Only openly declared attributes with widely agreed semantic types will provide machine actionability.
PID Meta Resolver	PID Meta Resolver (PIDMR) is a generic resolver that makes it possible to resolve PIDs from a wide variety of systems and providers.
PID Record	See Kernel Information.
PID Service Provider	An organisation which provides PID Services in conformance to a set of rules and standards defining the nature of a PID (PID Schema), subject to its controller, responsible for maintaining the rules for defining the integrity of PIDs (PID Authority).
PID Stack	A PID stack is a conceptual framework that includes the components required to ensure persistent identification and access.
Policy	A defined course of action or set of guiding principles for decision makers to achieve consistent, rational outcomes toward shared goals and values.

Prefix	A PID syntax component denoting an authority or division of a namespace. A prefix needs to be globally unique and associated with particular local authorities, which are free in how they generate locally unique IDs.
Referent	The entity or representation to which the PID resolves.
Schema	A set of rules and standards defining the nature of a Persistent Identifier (e.g. definition of associated metadata, quality assurance conditions, usage rights, terms and conditions, etc). The PID Schema should be machine-actionable.
Semantics	The meaning or interpretation of meaning attached to a given text string. It is recommended not to include semantics in an identifier string where meaning may change over time or may not be understood across linguistic and cultural divides.
Standards Body	The body, governance mechanism, or institution responsible for the maintenance of the standard(s) applicable to a schema.
Suffix	A suffix is the part of a unique and persistent identifier that is created by a local authority, which also specifies the syntax rules for the suffix.
Tombstone Information	A set of details associated with a deleted resource. It ensures that information can also be provided after the removal of an entity.

Appendix 3: Policy authors

The various versions of this policy were authored by different Working Groups, Task Forces and Expert Groups. The following lists detail the members of these groups.

Version 1.0

The authors of this version are a subset of members from the EOSC FAIR and EOSC Architecture Working Groups, as well as PID experts invited to contribute to the Architecture PID Task Force.

Name	EOSC Affiliation	Affiliation
Margareta Hellström	Architecture PID TF	Lund University and ICOS RI
André Heughebaert	FAIR WG	Belgian Biodiversity Platform
Rachael Kotarski	FAIR WG	British Library
Paolo Manghi	Architecture WG	ISTI/CNR
Brian Matthews	Architecture WG	UKRI-STFC
Raphael Ritz	Architecture WG	MPCDF/MPG
Anders Sparre Conrad	FAIR WG	Danish e-Infrastructure Cooperation
Mario Valle	Architecture PID TF	Swiss National Supercomputing Centre
Tobias Weigel	Architecture WG	DKRZ
Peter Wittenburg	FAIR WG	Max Planck Institute

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Name	EOSC Affiliation	Affiliation
Karel Luyben	Executive Board Co-Chair	CESAER
Cathrin Stöver	Executive Board Co-Chair	GÉANT
Jean-François Abramatic	Architecture WG Chair	Individual Expert
Juan Bicarregui	Rules of Participation WG Chair	Individual Expert
Jan Hrušák	Landscape WG Chair	Individual Expert
Sarah Jones	FAIR WG Chair	Individual Expert
Rupert Lück	Sustainability WG Co-Chair	EBML
Lidia Borrell-Damian	Sustainability WG Co-Chair	Science Europe
Natalia Manola	Skills and Training WG Chair	OpenAIRE
John Womersley		European Spallation Source ERIC
Ron Dekker		CESSDA
Jeannette Frey	Observer	LIBER

Version 1.2

Authors of this version were representatives of the EOSC-A PID Policy and Implementation Task Force.

Name	EOSC Affiliation	Affiliation
David Aymonin	EOSC-A PID TF	Abes - Agence bibliographique de l'enseignement supérieur
Gaëlle Bequet	EOSC-A PID TF	ISSN International Centre
Matthew Buys	EOSC-A PID TF	DataCite
Christian Cuciniello	EOSC-A PID TF	European Commission
Pablo De Castro	EOSC-A PID TF	euroCRIS
Tom Demeranville	EOSC-A PID TF	ORCID
Britta Dreyer	EOSC-A PID TF	Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB)
Nathalie Fargier	EOSC-A PID TF	CNRS-Inria-INRAE
Beate Guba	EOSC-A PID TF	TU Wien
Margareta Hellström	EOSC-A PID TF	ICOS ERIC
Tibor Kálmán	EOSC-A PID TF	GWDG
Florian Krebs	EOSC-A PID TF	German Aerospace Center (DLR)
Paolo Lai	EOSC-A PID TF	CNRS Inist
Jozef Mišutka	EOSC-A PID TF	Charles University
Tomasz Parkoła	EOSC-A PID TF	Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center

Name	EOSC Affiliation	Affiliation
Claudio Pisa	EOSC-A PID TF	GARR
Michal Růžička	EOSC-A PID TF	Masaryk University
Jochen Schirrwagen	EOSC-A PID TF	Bielefeld University
Stephan Siemen	EOSC-A PID TF	European Commission
Tommi Suominen	EOSC-A PID TF	CSC
Wojtek Sylwestrzak	EOSC-A PID TF	University of Warsaw
Mario Valle	EOSC-A PID TF	ETH Zürich - Swiss National Supercomputing Centre (CSCS)
Adam Vials Moore	EOSC-A PID TF	Jisc
Themis Zamani	EOSC-A PID TF	GRNET

Version 2.0

Authors of this version were representatives of the EOSC-A Opportunity Area 1 Expert Group: *Persistent Identifiers*.

Name	EOSC Affiliation	Affiliation
Raed Al Zoubi	FAIR Metrics and Data Quality TF Health Data Task Force TF	ASREN
Mike Bennett	FAIRCORE4EOSC	DataCite
Sharon Bolton	EOSC ENTRUST	University of Essex
Marek Cebecauer	FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects TF EOSC OAEG3	Heyrovsky Institute
Ellie DeSota	FAIR2ADAPT	DeSci Labs
Gorka Epelde	Health Data Task Force TF RAISE Advisory Board	Biogipuzkoa
Beate Guba	EOSC Support Office Austria	TU Wien
Margareta Hellström		Lund University
Wim Hugo	FAIRCORE4EOSC	DANS
Nick Juty	EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF FAIR-IMPACT	University of Manchester
Tibor Kálmán	OAEG1 Coordinator	GWDG
Evdokimos Konstantinidis	RAISE	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Paolo Lai	FAIR-IMPACT	CNRS Inist
Natascha van Lieshout	FAIRCORE4EOSC; FAIR-IMPACT	SURF

Name	EOSC Affiliation	Affiliation
Natascha van Lieshout	FAIRCORE4EOSC; FAIR-IMPACT	SURF
Gabriela Mejias	FAIR-IMPACT	DataCite
Paul Millar	EOSC OAE2 OSCARS	DESY
Adam Vials Moore	EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF FAIRCORE4EOSC	Jisc
Josefine Nordling	FAIR-IMPACT GraspOS	CSC
Michal Růžička	Long-Term Data Retention TF CRAFT-OA	Masaryk University
Tommi Suominen	EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF FAIRCORE4EOSC	CSC
Daniel Turner	FAIRCORE4EOSC; FAIR-IMPACT; Skills4EOSC	DCC
Ulriika Vihervalli	FAIRCORE4EOSC; EOSC-ENTRUST	CSC
Themis Zamani	FAIRCORE4EOSC	GRNET

Appendix 4: Versions and tracked changes

Version	Release date	Location	Changes from the previous version
v1.0 (1 st draft)	2019/12/13	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3574203	N/A
v1.0 (2 nd draft)	2020/05/01	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3780423	Numerous changes in response to feedback from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PIDapalooza 2020 • PID Forum • email and other personal feedback New DOI for Version 2.
v1.0	2020/09/30	https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/926037	Changes in response to feedback from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PID Forum • email and other personal feedback to the authors • Legal Interoperability WG, specifically on GDPR New DOI for final version.
v1.2	2024/02/19	Internal release by EOSC-A PID TF for the Opportunity Area Expert Group 1: Persistent Identifiers	Changes in response to feedback from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • discussions with the FAIRCORE4EOSC project • discussions with the FAIR-IMPACT project • EOSC Symposium 2023 session • International Data Week 2023 (IDW2023) • EOSC Winter School 2024 session
v2.0 (this version)	2024/03/27	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19250958	Changes in response to feedback from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OAEG1 - PID • EOSC Symposium 2024 • EOSC Winter School 2025 • EOSC EU Node

